

A ROBUST FACE DETECTION, AGE ESTIMATION AND GENDER PREDICTION BENCHMARK**Kongnyu Derek Ndi,**

Engr

- Assistant Lecturer, Department of Computer Engineering, National Higher Polytechnic Institute, The University of Bamenda, Bambili, Cameroon
- ORCID: 0009-0006-4665-4589

Onabid Mathias Akong,

PhD, Associate Professor

- Head of Department, Department of Computer Science, Higher Technical Teacher Training Collage, The University of Bamenda, Bambili, Cameroon

Pascaline Liaken Dickmu,

PhD, Associate Professor

- Head of Department, Department of Computer Engineering, National Higher Polytechnic Institute, The University of Bamenda, Bambili, Cameroon

Mama Nsangou Mouchili,

PhD

- Assistant Lecturer, Department of Computer Engineering, National Higher Polytechnic Institute, The University of Bamenda, Bambili, Cameroon
- ORCID: 0000-0002-5119-1586

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15591201>**Abstract**

In recent years, there is demand for advanced computer vision technologies particularly in areas like: facial detection and recognition, age estimation, and gender classification. However, the performance of machine learning models in these domains relies heavily on the availability of robust, diverse, and high-quality data. While existing datasets like the COCO, PASCAL VOC, Roboflow100, Adience, UTKFace, and IMDB-WIKI datasets etc., have made significant contributions, still some challenges in terms of demographic diversity, image quality, or annotations accuracy. Moreso, it is crucial to understand that due to image retrieval and annotation costs, most of these datasets consist largely of images found on the web and in some cases do not represent real-life ground truth age labels. As a result, it is difficult to assert with certainty the degree of generalization learned by models on these datasets. To address the aforementioned and support future research, we introduce new dataset, with the goal of advancing the state-of-the-art. Version one of this dataset contains rich human annotations, including face bounding boxes, ground truth age and gender for images of subjects in a natural uncontrolled environment. We obtain a total of 1000 participants videos captured, extracted images from the videos and made available annotations. Moreso, we compare performance using YOLO family state-of-the-art object detector trained on our dataset in comparison to other related benchmarks.

Keywords: Face detection, age estimation, gender classification, object detection, Dataset.

1 Introduction

Face detection is a necessary starting point for many related tasks, like face recognition, age estimation, gender classification, etc. which are integral components of numerous applications. With the rapid advancement in machine learning, the heart of such algorithms relies on large, diverse and well-annotated datasets that represent various environmental conditions and ground truth. Although several datasets have been released over the years, numerous things still challenge the performance of algorithms trained using them, but which are not limited only on the following aspects:

a. **Occlusion:** Greatly affects the ability of systems to detect the face as only a part of the face is visible.

b. **Lighting:** Not handling subject's variation in the lighting conditions in most datasets is an issue for face detection.

c. **Skin Color:** Some face detectors are biased toward some skin color due to limited race misrepresentation in most popular datasets.

d. **Unconstrained:** In-the-wild images, pose, expression, should be taken care of in deep learning models, as the faces in most datasets is unlikely to always be neutral in the real world

e. **Accurate Annotations:** Reliable age and gender labels are essential for training models, and some datasets contain inaccurate or coarse-grained labels.

f. **Image retrieval and annotation cost:** Most of the images found on these datasets are mostly scraped from the web with computed ages that mostly don't reflect ground truth and can't be sure of the generalization of models.

g. **Facial Expression:** Facial expressions should be taken care of when designing the features of a face or training a deep learning model, as the face is unlikely to always be neutral in the real world.

This paper introduces a robust dataset specifically designed to address most of the challenges mentioned in addition to contributions of existing benchmarks to support future research. The dataset offers high-resolution faces images with detailed annotations for face de-

tection bounding box, age and gender ground truth labels in natural real-life varying environmental conditions. We'll also explore data collection methods, ethical considerations, preprocessing, annotation techniques and experiments in comparison to related benchmarks. Our dataset has been meticulously human labeled with:

a. **Bounding Boxes for Face Detection:** Every face in an image has a bounding box that highlights the region for training face detection models.

b. **Age Annotations:** Images labelled with actual ground truth age actual age (as opposed to crowdsourced images where ground truth age is not readily available).

c. **Gender Labels:** Every face has been labeled with gender information (typically male or female).

2 Related Work

2.1 Introduction

We reviewed most of the latest remarkable and related datasets, some covering the tasks of one or more of either object detection, face detection, gender classification and age estimation. In benchmarking and evaluating different machine learning models, standardized datasets such as Microsoft COCO (Lin et al., 2014) and Pascal VOC (Everingham et al., 2010) are well-known dataset regularly used by researcher and engineers to train and evaluate computer vision models performance. The majority of facial image database are primarily recording of known participants in controlled environments (Grgic et al., 2011)(Ariz et al., 2016) or were based on a pre-recorded videos obtained from various media on the internet or movies(Dhall et al., 2007). Several other novel datasets have been introduced over the years. This literature review will cover some of these datasets, focusing on their contributions, challenges, and future prospects.

2.2 Face Detection Datasets

Face detection is a computer vision technique in which a computer program can detect the presence of human faces and also find their location in an image or a video stream. Over the past few years, new datasets have been created to address limitations of older datasets like Yale Face, LFW (Labeled Faces in the Wild), and FDDB (Face Detection Data Set and Benchmark), by expanding the variety of conditions under which face detection must perform. These newer datasets aim to capture more diverse populations, challenging scenarios, and real-world variances. Here's an overview of recent novel face detection datasets:

FDDB (Face Detection Dataset and Benchmark) (Hsu et al., 2010). The dataset contains 2845 images with 5171 faces annotations, where images are also of various resolution, e.g. 363x450 and 229x410, while each face is annotated with a pre-define ellipse instead of bounding box. The dataset incorporates a range of challenges, including difficult pose angles, out-of-focus faces and low resolution. Both greyscale and color images are included.

Annotated Faces in the Wild (AFW) (Zhu & Ramanan, 2012). AFW dataset, is made up of 205 images collected from Flickr with 468 labelled faces in total. Annotations include a rectangular bounding box, 6 landmarks and the pose angles. AFW is often used for

landmark estimation in real-world, cluttered images, face detection, and pose estimation.

Multi-Attribute Labelled Faces (MALF) (B. Yang et al., 2015) which is a large dataset designed for fine-grained evaluation of face detection in the wild which contains 5,250 images collected from the Internet and ~12,000 labelled faces.

WIDERR Face Dataset. The WIDER FACE dataset, proposed by (S. Yang et al., 2015), is one of the largest and most challenging datasets for face detection. It contains 32,203 images with 393,703 labeled faces. The dataset is characterized by high variability in scale, occlusion, pose, and background clutter. It introduces three levels of difficulty: easy, medium, and hard, based on the visibility and resolution of the faces. This dataset has become a benchmark for evaluating the robustness of face detection algorithms under challenging real-world conditions.

CelebA Dataset. The CelebA dataset is widely used for both face detection and recognition. Released by (Z. Liu et al., 2015) it contains over 200,000 celebrity images from more than 10,000 identities. Although initially intended for face attribute recognition, its large-scale face images with rich annotations make it useful for face detection tasks. The dataset provides 5 landmark locations, 40 binary attributes, and tight bounding box labels for faces, making it highly versatile for face detection and beyond.

MegaFace(2016) & MegaFace 2.0 (2020). Initially focused on facial recognition, MegaFace (Miller et al., 2015) became a valuable dataset for face detection tasks due to its large-scale nature. MegaFace 2.0 expanded the original dataset, adding better annotations for face detection, including bounding boxes and enhanced demographic diversity. It contains over 1 million images and 690,000 identities, making it an essential dataset for large-scale face detection.

- Strengths: Large scale, diverse identities, and images.

- Limitations: Heavy focus on recognition; less on real-time detection.

IMDB-WIKI Dataset. Although introduced slightly before 2018, the IMDB-WIKI dataset is notable for its contribution to age estimation and face detection tasks. This dataset contains over 500,000 images of celebrities extracted from IMDb and Wikipedia, offering a rich source for training robust face detection algorithms with an emphasis on age variation (Rothe et al., 2018)

- Strengths: Large scale, real-world images
- Limitations: A significant challenge with the IMDB-WIKI dataset is the presence of noisy labels. The age and gender labels are inferred from metadata like IMDb birthdates or Wikipedia info boxes, which may not always be accurate.

CelebA-HQ 2020 (Xia et al., 2021). CelebA-HQ is an upgraded version of the CelebA dataset, which focuses on high-resolution images and detailed annotations. It consists of 30,000 images with 40 attribute labels per image, making it suitable for both face detection and attribute prediction tasks. The high-quality nature of the images has enabled significant advances

in generative models and high-fidelity face recognition systems.

2.3 Gender and Age Datasets

Adience (Eidinger et al., 2014). Contains over 26,000 images labeled with age and gender, focused on a diverse range of ages.

- **Strengths:** Includes variations in age, gender, and pose

- **Limitations:** Images often taken in uncontrolled environments, leading to variability in quality.

FG-NET (Lanitis et al., 2002) A dataset with 1,002 images of faces at different ages, annotated with ages ranging from 0 to 69 years.

- **Strengths:** High-quality images focused on age progression

- **Limitations:** Limited to a smaller number of subjects at less diversity in backgrounds

MORPH (Ricanek & Tesafaye, 2006) Contains over 55,000 images with ages ranging from 16 to 77 years, emphasizing longitudinal changes in faces.

- **Strengths:** Good for studying age progression and changes over time.

- **Limitations:** Primarily focused on a specific demographic group, which may limit generalizability.

Conclusion. These are some of the most famous datasets containing both age and gender ground truth. They have been widely used in academic research and have helped advance facial recognition technology. However, significant limitations, particularly in terms of label accuracy, image quality, and representation of different ethnic and age groups still exist. This new benchmark handles most of the existing limitations with the hope for future improvements.

3 Methodology

Ethical approval declarations

The study was approved by the Faculty of Health Science review board of the University of Bamenda ref: 51745551, and informed consent was obtained from all individual participants, including parental or legal guardian via a consent form that the use of their images, is ONLY for academic research.

3.1 Data Collection

The data collection team captured participants shoulder level face video in uncontrolled daylight environment mostly in the University of Bamenda campus, residential areas, public spaces, and along student hostel areas. All the videos were recorded manually in normal classroom with outdoor and indoor light as the only source of illumination by trained data collectors. Capture equipment included: professional digital video cameras and mobile devices so we can have a blend of varying resolutions. The data collection period span over two semesters. First, pre-defined questions were carefully chosen to be asked during actual recording to ensure varying pose and facial expressions. During the video record, participants stood distances ranging 1m to 3m distance in front of camera at shoulder level and responded to pre-defined questions. To assure complete capture of each subject face, head rotation from -90 to +90 and +180 to -180 degrees.

3.2 Data Preprocessing

All video data collect was human verified and selected to guarantee large diversity of facial appearances. 18% of the raw data was discarded for not meeting the data requirements, due to poorly capture and gender balancing. The videos were all manually labeled with actual age based on participants date of birth, gender [Female (0) or Male (1)], ethnicity, participant unique code number (uuid). The unique code number serves as primary key in our excel sheet storing participant bio-information (level of education, region of origin, tribe, religion, nationality, age ranges) which could serve the requirements of related researches making use of this dataset. Images were manually extracted from videos using Roboflow (Version 1.0) [Software] (Dwyer et al., 2024) at a frame rate of 2 fps (minimum) and 10 fps (maximum). All images were resized to 640x 640 pixels to maintain uniformity and stored in jpg format. No data augmentation and other preprocessing steps were applied manually.

3.3 Data Annotation

A multi-step process was used for annotation to ensure accuracy since data annotation plays a crucial role in ensuring the accurate functioning of numerous machine learning algorithms. The process of annotating objects (faces) in all images found in this dataset is labor-intensive in nature, and it involves significant time commitment especially when done manually. The first step of annotation was done manually by human annotators whereby, face in images identified were annotated with bounding boxes and categorized by assigning them the appropriate class label (face). Moreso, we annotated an image for a particular scenario only once while skipping same repetitive images as it may cause problems of overfitting models (Aghabagherloo et al., 2025). In the second step, we use semi-automated annotation using Roboflow Auto Label (Dwyer et al., 2024) lets you use large foundation vision trained models to automatically label images. Our choice of a foundation was model was the pre-trained object detection model called Grounding DINO proposed in (S. Liu et al., 2023). The model achieves remarkable results, such as 5.25AP on COCO zero-shot. So, the predictions from this model were verified and approved for all images by human annotators.

A total of 10,000 images were extracted from the video capture, and a total of 7,142 images chosen for inclusion in this study. Each image has only one subject, resulting to 7,142 annotated images with corresponding generated 7,142 labels with their respective 1 class (face) presented in table 1. For the annotation of images, we used different formats to hold class label and bounding box coordinates. The images are annotated with four key attributes:

- 1)**Face Bounding boxes:** We provide bbox coordinate (xmin, ymin, xmax, ymax) for all images

- 2)**Age:** Each image is labeled with the individual's actual age, ranging from infants (2 years) to seniors (90+ years).

- 3)**Gender:** The dataset includes a binary label for gender, categorized as male (1) and female (0), while

recognizing the limitations of this binary approach. Future versions may incorporate non-binary gender annotations.

4)**Ethnicity**: The dataset is annotated to reflect the ethnic diversity of individuals

5)**External Excel Sheet**: It comprises additional bio-information for all participants

Figure 1: Roboflow annotation editor

3.4 Dataset Statistics

The dataset contains 7,142 high-resolution images, see table 1 on regional spread. In terms of the image data, all collected images are RGB images in JPEG format. We labeled all videos for age, gender and ethnicity using the following format age_gender_ethnicity_uuid_genericVideoName.jpg. Each image contains 1 face averagely, with 85% of images contain one face, 12.7% contain 2~4 faces and 2.3% contain zero face just empty background. All faces have bounding box annotations, no augmentation techniques were applied to generate additional data, so researchers can apply such techniques as maybe required. We have applied 70% (5k images) for training, 20% (1.4k images) for validation set and 10% (715 images) for test set.

Table 1

Number of dataset participants based on gender and regional spread

Gender	Number of labeled subjects	Region of Origin	
		Count	Region
Male	524	218	Northwest
		110	West
		96	Littoral
		100	Southwest
Female	476	264	Northwest
		95	West
		50	Littoral
		67	West
Total	1,000		

Figure II: Age representation in our Dataset. Majority of the volunteer were University undergraduate students

4 Experiments and Evaluations

We trained popular state-of-the-art object detection model YOLO (You Only Look Once) on our dataset and presented comparative evaluation results for variants of YOLO (Tian et al., 2025). We compared results on related datasets using the same YOLO versions as reported in their publish papers. We trained models with default hyperparameters for 100 epochs at 640x640 resolution.

Mean Average Precision based on YOLOv5, YOLOv7, and YOLOv11.

Dataset	YOLOv5	YOLOv7	YOLOv11
	mAP@.50		
Roboflow100 (Ciaglia et al., 2022)	0.752 ¹³	0.699 ¹⁴	-
COCO (Anh Nguyen et al., 2024)	0.763	0.6132	-
PASCAL VOC (Anh Nguyen et al., 2024)	0.8235	0.5038	-
Ours	0.994	0.927	0.995

Figure III: YOLO11 training and loss graphs'

Figure IV: Confusion matrix

¹³ Real World Category

¹⁴ Real World Category

Figure 5: YOLOv5 training and loss graphs

Figure VI: YOLOv5 validation labels

Figure 7: YOLOv5 F1 curve

5 Results and Discussion

We observed that the performance of some YOLO variants models trained on our dataset outperforms those on three related datasets reported in their papers, which could be due to the goals we achieved. Firstly, our benchmark provides key performance features such as high-quality images and annotations, increased diversity and challenging conditions such as occlusion and poor lighting demonstrating the superior quality. Secondly, we have made data annotation available in a variety of formats: - JSON, XML, TXT, CSV, and others to ease the integration and usage format for other

researchers. In literature, it shows that there is variation in model performance between models across datasets (Hatamian et al., 2025). It means that a given model may perform better on one dataset and worse on another. For now, we do not investigate the reason for performance differences, but our results suggest that there are significant improvements on our dataset since it performs better across all variants of YOLO models. But we are mindful of the fact that there is still need to likely make significant improvements on object detection models to expect a wider coverage performance on custom datasets that they may be applied to.

Figure VIII: Sample dataset images with age and gender labels

We deployed YOLOv11 object detection models trained using our dataset and test for face detection on test images on Roboflow. Figure VIII shows a bounding box along the coordinates of the face detected in the image.

Figure IX: Deployed YOLOv11 prediction at 50% confidence threshold

6 Conclusion

We introduce a robust dataset for face detection, age and gender benchmark with ground truth labels and annotations to encourage the evaluation of model performance and generalizability in the real world. It offers significant improvements over existing datasets in terms of diversity, image quality, and annotation accuracy. Our initial evaluation shows that it is a valuable resource for researchers and developers in the field of computer vision, enabling the development of more robust and reliable models that can perform well in real-world conditions.

7 Acknowledgements

We thank the staff and management of National Higher Polytechnique Institute (NAHPI), also top management of the University of Bamenda. We immensely thank the student body of the National Higher Polytechnique Institute and the University of Bamenda, for their active participation in providing the data used for the creation of the dataset presented in this paper. We thank especially, Tata Ronaldo Wiysanyuy, Tantoh Telmah,

Kinyuy, Tanyu Brandon Sosah, Pavel Yegha Semma, Njong Bingeh Afumbom Emy, Nji Mariette Therese Neh, Ngwingche Epongseh Alomba, Ngwa Emmanuel Fuh, Munda Bladini Fru Tanda, Nchanji Faithful Ngirnyu, Nchinde Tandjong Josue, Nde Alban Atsoh, Ndeh Cedric Kubang Kum, Ndzelen Glen Afoni, Neba Japhate Ambe Azinwi, Nfon Jeannoel Agahnui, Afungfe Henriette, Akia Samuel Cha, Atud Konfor Jerry, Akih Sinet Akihduh, Awatsop Fopa Jeff Jason, Binwi Ane Naomi Binda, Botambuh Fabrice Bauket, Carl Ghogeh Vezhugho, Che Neba Jr Kome, Chelsea Banke, Chi Karl Junior, Clement Nyuywyse Tirnyuy Maimo, Egbe Job Nkwa, Ejoh Hosea Nwongwe, Emmanuel Talacla Tiwa Tchoffo, Ewala Endah Asakwa Ayeintin, Fien Dora Bangha, Fifen Ngapna Blatere, Fokou Winny Channele, Fombi Magnus-Favour, Fon Roland Mbanwei, Fondzenyuy Cecilia Berinyuy, Fotsing Tchoupe Mathieu Boris, Ihimbru Kanyimi Ihimbru, Kenne Lontsi Marius, Kimbi Christelle, Kom Zeking Paule Ursulla, Mba-Atanga Jude Aghedseh, Mbiyongwoh Cedrick Anushiny, Medzengue Cyrille

Junior, Mengjo Nama Anna Thelma, Miki Dingana, Mofor Emmanuel Nkwenti, Nfon Joseph Azenui. We also extend our thanks to parents for giving concern: Late Prof. Emeritus & Senator Carl Mbofung Moses Funtong, Darkang Fanta, Fola Juliet Ndi, Anye Divine, Stephen Maboh, Magdaline Leinyuy, Nfor Emmanuel, Laisin Jones, Chuye Edwin, Stanley Massa, Tanyu Elvis, Tse Etan, Maboh Divine Favor, Anye Divine, Anye Jayden Correy, Anye Miya Limnyuy, Venita Ghaife. We also thank the senior pastor of Christ Memorial Baptist Church, Rev. Dr. Ngankeng Eric for facilitating data collectors to carry out sensitization in church. We sincerely thank everyone who facilitated in one way or the other whose names are not mentioned.

References:

1. Aghabagherloo, A., Abadi, A., Sarkar, S., Dasu, V. A., & Preneel, B. (2025). Impact of Data Duplication on Deep Neural Network-Based Image Classifiers: Robust vs. Standard Models. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2504.00638v1>
2. Anh Nguyen, L., Dat Tran, M., & Son, Y. (2024). Empirical Evaluation and Analysis of YOLO Models in Smart Transportation. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ai5040122>
3. Ariz, M., Bengoechea, J. J., Villanueva, A., & Cabeza, R. (2016). A novel 2D/3D database with automatic face annotation for head tracking and pose estimation. *Computer Vision and Image Understanding*, 148, 201–210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CVIU.2015.04.009>
4. Ciaglia, F., Zuppichini, F. S., Guerrie, P., McQuade, M., & Solawetz, J. (2022). Roboflow 100: A Rich, Multi-Domain Object Detection Benchmark. <http://arxiv.org/abs/2211.13523>
5. Dhall, A., Member, S., Goecke, R., Lucey, S., & Gedeon, T. (2007). Collecting Large, Richly Annotated Facial-Expression Databases from Movies. 6(1).
6. Dwyer, B., Nelson, J., & Hansen, T. (2024). Roboflow (Version 1.0) [Software].
7. Eidinger, E., Enbar, R., & Hassner, T. (2014). Age and gender estimation of unfiltered faces. *IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security*, 9(12), 2170–2179. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIFS.2014.2359646>
8. Everingham, M., Van Gool, L., Williams, C. K. I., Winn, J., & Zisserman, A. (2010). The pascal visual object classes (VOC) challenge. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 88(2), 303–338. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11263-009-0275-4>
9. Grgic, M., Delac, K., & Grgic, S. (2011). SCface - Surveillance cameras face database. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 51(3), 863–879. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11042-009-0417-2/METRICS>
10. Hatamian, A., Levine, L., Oskouie, H. E., & Sarrafzadeh, M. (2025). Exploring the Impact of Dataset Statistical Effect Size on Model Performance and Data Sample Size Sufficiency.
11. Hsu, G. S., Tran, T. H., & Chung, S. L. (2010). Benchmark face detection using a face recognition database. *Proceedings - International Conference on Image Processing, ICIP*, 3821–3824. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIP.2010.5654037>
12. Lanitis, A., Taylor, C. J., & Cootes, T. F. (2002). Toward automatic simulation of aging effects on face images. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 24(4), 442–455. <https://doi.org/10.1109/34.993553>
13. Lin, T. Y., Maire, M., Belongie, S., Hays, J., Perona, P., Ramanan, D., Dollár, P., & Zitnick, C. L. (2014). Microsoft COCO: Common Objects in Context. *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (Including Subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, 8693 LNCS(PART 5), 740–755. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-10602-1_48
14. Liu, S., Zeng, Z., Ren, T., Li, F., Zhang, H., Yang, J., Jiang, Q., Li, C., Yang, J., Su, H., Zhu, J., & Zhang, L. (2023). Grounding DINO: Marrying DINO with Grounded Pre-Training for Open-Set Object Detection. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-72970-6_3
15. Liu, Z., Luo, P., Wang, X., & Tang, X. (2015). Deep Learning Face Attributes in the Wild .
16. Miller, D., Brossard, E., Seitz, S., & Kemelmacher-Shlizerman, I. (2015). MegaFace: A Million Faces for Recognition at Scale. <http://megaface.cs.washington.edu/toparticipateinthechallenge>.
17. Ricanek, K., & Tesafaye, T. (2006). MORPH: a longitudinal image database of normal adult age-progression. *7th International Conference on Automatic Face and Gesture Recognition (FGR06)*, 341–345. <https://doi.org/10.1109/FGR.2006.78>
18. Rothe, R., Timofte, R., & Gool, L. Van. (2018). Deep expectation of real and apparent age from a single image without facial landmarks. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 126, 144–157.
19. Tian, Y., Ye, Q., & Doermann, D. (2025). YOLOv12: Attention-Centric Real-Time Object Detectors. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2502.12524v1>
20. Xia, W., Yang, Y., Xue, J.-H., & Wu, B. (2021). Towards Open-World Text-Guided Face Image Generation and Manipulation. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2104.08910v1>
21. Yang, B., Yan, J., Lei, Z., & Li, S. Z. (2015). Fine-grained evaluation on face detection in the wild. *2015 11th IEEE International Conference and Workshops on Automatic Face and Gesture Recognition, FG 2015*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/FG.2015.7163158>
22. Yang, S., Luo, P., Loy, C. C., & Tang, X. (2015). WIDER FACE: A Face Detection Benchmark. *Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 2016-December*, 5525–5533. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2016.596>
23. Zhu, X., & Ramanan, D. (2012). Face detection, pose estimation, and landmark localization in the wild. *Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2879–2886. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2012.6248014>